

An overview on photoinduced bimolecular electron transfer (ET) in constrained reaction media[†]

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Abstract : Understanding the kinetic and mechanistic details of the electron transfer (ET) reactions in constrained media is an area of intense research in chemical sciences. The well known Marcus outer-sphere ET theory predicted an interesting inversion behavior for the ET rates with reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$), which remains debatable for last more than fifty years for bimolecular ET reactions, though clear Marcus Inversion (MI) behaviors have been well documented for many intramolecular ET systems. For bimolecular ET reactions in conventional solvents, the observed reaction rate at the higher exergonicities usually reach a saturation limit equal to the bimolecular diffusional rate (k_d), displaying the typical Rehm-Weller behavior than the theoretically predict MI behavior. Though many explanations have been put forward to justify the observed Rehm-Weller behavior for the bimolecular ET rates with reaction exergonicity, research had been continuing to find out the means that can overcome the limitations associated with the bimolecular ET reactions and can lead to appearance of the theoretically predicted MI behavior even for the bimolecular ET reactions. With this perspective and considering that the ET reactions are the most fundamental reactions occurring ubiquitously in chemistry and biology, extensive studies have been pursued on bimolecular ET reactions for last many decades to understand all the intricate details that can modulate the kinetics of such fundamental reactions. For last about one and half decades, our extensive efforts to understand bimolecular photoinduced ET (PET) reactions under various experimental conditions have made us to explore the requisite situations for the reaction environments that can favorably assist in realizing the MI behavior for bimolecular PET reactions. It has been comprehended from our studies that using constrained reaction media like microheterogeneous surfactant assemblies like micelles, reverse micelles, etc., or high viscosity and slow relaxing solvents like ionic liquids, the MI behavior is observed very easily for bimolecular PET reactions, assisted jointly by ultraslow reactant diffusion and exceedingly slow solvent relaxation dynamics compared to the ET rates. In this article we provide an overview of various aspects of bimolecular ET reactions bringing out how the constrained reaction media help in realizing MI behavior even for such bimolecular ET reactions.

Keywords : Electron transfer reaction, Marcus Inversion behavior, constrained reaction media, one-dimensional and two-dimensional ET models.

Introduction

Electron transfer (ET) is the most fundamental reaction ubiquitously occurring in chemistry and biology¹⁻²⁵. All oxidation-reduction processes occurring in chemistry and biology invariably involve the ET reactions in some forms. In biology, ET plays a very vital role, often acting as a trigger to initiate sequences of the follow-up reactions leading to the de-

sired outcome of the complex biological processes¹⁷⁻²⁵. Photosynthesis in green plants is the most important example of the ET mediated process in the Mother Nature that produces food for the whole living world, through the direct utilization of the solar energy. In chemistry as well as in chemical technology, the ET reactions play very important roles. Artificial solar energy conversion mechanisms, photography, xerogra-

[†]Professor D. P. Chakraborty 60th Birth Anniversary Lecture (2016).

phy, molecular electronics, photovoltaics, information storage, and in many such important technological areas the ET reactions are directly associated with the overall chemical processes involved therein^{1-16,26-32}. Due to such immense importance, the ET reactions have attracted enormous research interests of the scientists for many decades to explore various fundamental aspects of the ET reactions, both experimentally and theoretically¹⁻⁶⁷. Though ET reaction in its literary term implies the transfer of an electron from a donor (D) moiety to an acceptor (A) moiety, in regard to the energetics and dynamics involved in the ET reactions in various D/A systems are unexpectedly complex as the actual reaction is controlled by a large number of energetic/dynamic factors that are yet to be understood very explicitly. Accordingly, studies on the ET reactions in various D/A systems and different reaction environments still remain to be very active research area in the contemporary chemical and biological sciences.

For most ET systems involving organic donor (D) and acceptor (A) molecules, the transfer of an electron from the ground state D to the ground state A is not favorable from energetic considerations. Interestingly, however, when either of these reactants (D or A) is promoted to the excited electronic state, e.g. following photoexcitation of the molecule, the ET reaction in the concerned D*/A or A*/D pair often becomes energetically very favorable. This happens because the excess energy provided to the D* or A* molecule through photoexcitation acts favorably to increase the effective reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$) for the ET process in the D*/A or A*/D pair as compared to that of the ET reaction involving the D/A pair where both the reactants are in the ground state¹⁻⁴⁴. Accordingly, studies on the photoinduced ET (PET) reactions have been used very extensively to understand the mechanistic and kinetic details of the ET reactions involving various D/A systems under various experimental conditions¹⁻⁶⁷.

In many organic D/A systems, the PET reactions usually occur in the fast to ultrafast time scales, lead-

ing the ET times to appear in the nanosecond to sub-picosecond time domains¹⁻⁵⁴. Accordingly, to explore the kinetic and dynamic details of such PET reactions it is essential to use the short or ultra-short laser pulses to initiate the excitation of D/A system and a similarly fast or ultrafast detection technique is required to monitor the progress of the PET reaction. Thus, fast and ultrafast fluorescence or transient absorption based photochemical techniques are realized to be the best methods to investigate the kinetics of most PET reactions in organic D/A systems. In the last couple of decades such fast and ultrafast PET studies in both homogeneous and heterogeneous media have been investigated quite extensively, exploring many intricate details of the ET reactions¹⁻⁶⁷. In spite of such extensive studies, many details of the PET reactions, especially those of the bimolecular PET reactions under constrained reaction media, are still remained to be understood very clearly^{10-12,68-90}. Accordingly studies on bimolecular PET reactions in constrained solvent media are still the subject of intense research in contemporary chemical sciences, aiming to arrive at a comprehensive understanding of the various factors that control the bimolecular ET reactions under such typical reaction environments that have many applied interests.

In general, for a PET reaction, the concerned D and A moieties can either be covalently linked to each other or they can be isolated molecules randomly distributed in the reaction media. Accordingly, PET reactions can either be of intramolecular or intermolecular (also called bimolecular) in nature. In both the cases, if for simplicity we assume that the acceptor moiety is photoexcited to initiate the PET reaction, the intramolecular and bimolecular PET reactions can be represented as in their simplest forms as shown in Scheme 1. Following this scheme, it is evident that for intramolecular PET the experimentally estimated rate constant (k_{obs}) following the decay kinetics of A* in the bound A*-D system would be exactly equal to the rate constant (k_{et}) for the intrinsic ET step. For bimolecular PET, however, the experi-

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(a) Intramolecular PET Reaction:

(b) Bimolecular PET Reaction:

Scheme 1. Representations of the intramolecular and bimolecular PET reactions, in their simplest forms, considering that the acceptor molecule is made in the excited state following photoexcitation to undergo ET reaction with the ground state donor molecule.

mentally estimated k_{obs} following the decay kinetics of free A^* cannot often be just equal to the k_{et} for the intrinsic ET step, because, in this case the randomly distributed free A^* and D molecules are first required to be brought within the zone of the reaction sphere through diffusion process to form the precursor (or encounter) complex $[A^*/D]$, and the ET reactions can eventually take place only in these precursor/encounter complexes. Accordingly, in this case, the k_{obs} will be a function of both diffusional rate constant (k_d) and the intrinsic ET rate constant (k_{et}). Moreover, for bimolecular PET reactions, the contact ion-pair state $[A^-/D^+]$ which is formed by ET reaction in the precursor/encounter complex can subsequently undergo number of follow-up reactions, namely, reverse ET reaction (k_{-et}), ion dissociation process (k_{ID}), charge recombination process (k_{CR}), chemical reactions (k_r), etc., and all these processes can influence the experimental k_{obs} value, as all the processes are coupled to each other. It is thus evident that the observed kinetics of the bimolecular PET reactions would inherently be very complicated as compared to that of the intramolecular PET reactions.

As it is understandable from the above discussions, the overall bimolecular PET reaction should be represented better by the following explicit reaction Scheme 2, where intrinsic ET step in the encounter complex is just an elementary step among the other processes associated to the ET reaction in a coupled manner. Obviously, exploration of the kinetic details for the bimolecular ET reaction in a solution is inherently a very complex proposition. Further, studies on the bimolecular PET reactions become far more com-

plex when such ET reactions are intended to be carried out in a constrained reaction medium, i.e. in a solvent medium where the diffusion of the reactant molecules are quite restricted and also the distributions of the reactant molecules in the medium are quite inhomogeneous, either due to the topology of the reaction medium or due to the slow diffusion of the reactants and slow relaxation of the solvent system, as compared to the time-scales of the ET reactions. In the following discussion we will systematically present the general aspects of the ET reactions, bringing out sequentially the important features of the bimolecular PET reaction in constrained media, as this is the topic of our concern for the present review article^{10-12,68-90}.

Scheme 2. Elementary steps involved in bimolecular PET reactions; k_d is the bimolecular diffusion controlled rate constant for encounter complex ($[A^*/D]$) formation, k_{-d} is the diffusion mediated dissociation constant for disintegration of the $[A^*/D]$ complex, k_{et} is the intrinsic rate constant for ET in the $[A^*/D]$ complex, k_{-et} is the rate constant for reverse ET from the contact ion-pair state $[A^-/D^+]$, and k_p is the sum of all the rate constants associated with the decay processes of $[A^-/D^+]$ excluding the reverse ET step.

Theoretical background of Marcus ET theory : Inversion behavior for ET rates with reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$)

The phenomenal theoretical treatment to correlate the rates of the outer-sphere ET reactions (occur without making or breaking any bond) with the concerned free energy changes (ΔG^0) of the reactions was provided by Professor Rudolph A. Marcus back in 1956 which is now universally known as the Marcus outer-sphere ET theory. Considering the versatility of this theory and finding its extreme utilizations in understanding various ET reactions, Professor Marcus was awarded with the Nobel Prize in chemistry in the year 1992. Though the original Marcus ET theory

was proposed based on the classical concept of the simple outer-sphere ET reaction^{32,45,46}, the concept, however, received many refinements during the course of its long journey, incorporating both semi-classical and quantum mechanical aspects into the backbone of the original outer-sphere ET theory^{1-10,32,45-67}.

Based on the Marcus outer-sphere ET theory, either in its classical form or on incorporating the semi-classical concept into the original theory, the rate constant k_{et} for the intrinsic ET step in Scheme 1 should be expressed in its simplified form as^{1-10,32,45-67},

$$k_{\text{et}} = \nu \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta G^*}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

where the pre-exponential factor ν is the effective frequency factor for the intrinsic ET reaction, ΔG^* is the free energy of activation, R is the universal gas constant and T is the absolute temperature. In its explicit form, the frequency factor ν is in fact the product of two terms, namely, the nuclear frequency factor, ν_n , and the electronic transmission coefficient, κ_{el} . The term ν_n represents the frequency at which the reactant state passes through the transition state (TS) region of the ET reaction and the term κ_{el} represents the probability by which the reactant state (R) can transform to the product state (P) as the reacting system passes through the TS. Though in the classical form of the Marcus ET theory the parameter κ_{el} was considered to be unity, however, following the semi-classical model of the Marcus ET theory, the value of κ_{el} should be determined by the extent of electronic coupling matrix element (V_{el}) between the R and P states and should be given as^{1-10,32,45-67},

$$\kappa_{\text{et}} = \frac{1}{1 + (4\pi V_{\text{el}}^2 \tau_s / \hbar \lambda)} \quad (2)$$

where τ_s is the time constant for the solvent relaxation process around the reacting system and λ is the total reorganization energy associated with the concerned ET reaction. It is evident from eq. (2) that if

V_{el} between the R and P states is very strong ($V_{\text{el}} \gg 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), κ_{el} will be very close to unity, making the ET reaction to occur with an adiabatic mechanism. On the contrary, if V_{el} is significantly low ($V_{\text{el}} \ll 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), κ_{el} becomes much less than unity, causing the ET reaction to proceed following the non-adiabatic mechanism^{1-10,32,45-67}.

In Marcus outer-sphere ET theory, it is considered that along the unified reaction coordinate the free energy of both reactant (R) and product (P) states varies in a quadratic manner. It is further assumed that the force constant for the quadratic function for the free energy of both R and P states is effectively the same for an outer-sphere ET reaction. Thus, considering the unified reaction coordinate X as the normalized coordinate such that the free energy minimum for the R state would appear at $X = 0$ and that of the P state would appear at $X = 1$, the free energies for the R and P states (G_{R} and G_{P} , respectively) as a function of X can be expressed as^{1-10,32,45-67}.

$$G_{\text{R}} = \lambda X^2 \quad (3)$$

$$G_{\text{P}} = \lambda (1 - X)^2 + \Delta G^0 \quad (4)$$

where λ is the total reorganization energy of the ET reaction and it is the function of the associated force constant (k) for the R and P states (i.e. $\lambda = k/2$) and ΔG^0 is the standard free energy change between the minima of the P and R states. The free energy relations for R and P states, represented by eqs. (3) and (4), can also be graphically presented as in Fig. 1 for their easier visualization.

Based on eqs. (3) and (4) and considering Panel A in Fig. 1, if X_c is the crossing point of the G_{R} and G_{P} curves along the X coordinate, which presents the TS for the ET reaction, one can write^{1-10,32,45-67},

$$\lambda X_c^2 = \lambda (1 - X_c)^2 + \Delta G^0 \quad (5)$$

By solving eq. (5) we can therefore express X_c as,

$$X_c = \frac{\lambda + \Delta G^0}{2\lambda} \quad (6)$$

Accordingly, the expression for the free energy of

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Fig. 1. Quadratic free energy curves for R and P states as considered in Marcus outer-sphere ET theory. Panel A is shown to represent the situation involving the classical ET model and Panel B is shown to represent the situation involving the semi-classical ET model. Different energy terms as appear in eqs. (1), (3) and (4) are indicated in the panels for their easy realization.

activation for the ET reaction can be obtained as,

$$\Delta G^* = \lambda X_c^2 = \lambda \left(\frac{\lambda + \Delta G^0}{2\lambda} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{\lambda + \Delta G^0}{4\lambda} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

Substituting this expression for ΔG^* in the simplified form of the k_{et} expression in eq. (1), a somewhat more explicit expression for k_{et} can be given as,

$$k_{et} = v \exp \frac{-(\lambda + \Delta G^0)^2}{4\lambda RT} \quad (8)$$

Since the reorganization energy λ is always a positive quantity, eq. (8) suggests that the ET process would turn out to be barrierless (i.e. $\Delta G^* = 0$) when the exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$) of the reaction becomes equal to λ . This would naturally represent the situation for the maximum k_{et} value possible for an ET system. One can now easily visualize that for the exergonicity region lower than the barrierless condition, there will be a gradual decrease in ΔG^* with the increasing

Fig. 2. Graphical presentation of the appearance of Marcus inversion for ET rates as the exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$) of the reaction increases. Qualitative presentation of the type of free energy crossings of the R and P states for the three typical situations of ET under normal region, barrierless condition and inversion region are also shown in the figure.

exergonicity for the ET reaction (*cf.* eq. (7)), leading the k_{et} value to increase asymptotically with the increasing $-\Delta G^0$ till one reaches the maximum k_{et} value at the barrierless condition. This is the region we refer as the normal Marcus region. Similarly, at the exergonicity region higher than the barrierless condition, there would be a gradual increase in ΔG^* with the increasing exergonicity (*cf.* eq. (7)), leading the k_{et} value to decrease gradually on increasing the $-\Delta G^0$ beyond the barrierless condition. This is the region we refer as the Marcus inversion region. It is thus evident from the consideration of the Marcus outer-sphere ET theory that the k_{et} values should follow an inverted bell-shaped correlation curve as the exergonicity of the ET reaction is changed from the very low to the very high values covering the barrierless condition of the ET reaction, which can pictorially be presented as in Fig. 2 for a qualitative representation.

Experimental evidences of Marcus Inversion behavior

Though inversion behavior in the ET rates with reaction exergonicity was predicted by Professor Marcus in his famous outer-sphere ET theory^{45,46} well back in the year 1956, in spite of enormous efforts by many researchers it took almost 30 years to

realize this unique Marcus Inversion (MI) behavior experimentally for the first time by Miller and coworkers¹⁰² in the year 1984. These authors convincingly demonstrated the MI behavior for the first time following the intramolecular charge shift reactions in the pulse radiolytically produced radical species in the thoughtfully designed donor-spacer-acceptor (D-S-A) kind of bi-functional chemical systems suitable for intramolecular ET reaction (*cf.* Scheme 1). The exemplary D-S-A kind of bi-functional systems used by Miller and coworkers¹⁰² in their seminal work on MI behavior are shown in Scheme 3. Subsequently, the same research group extended their studies on intramolecular ET reactions involving other more extended series of D-S-A systems, reconfirming experimentally the presence of MI behavior for intramolecular ET reactions¹⁰³.

Scheme 3. The D-S-A kind of chemical systems used by Millers and coworkers¹⁰² in their study demonstrating MI behavior for the first time experimentally using intramolecular charge shift reactions in the pulse radiolytically produced radicals in these chemical systems.

Convincing experimental demonstration of MI behavior for intramolecular ET reaction was also reported in the subsequent year by Wasielewski and coworkers¹⁰⁴, following the photoinduced radical ion-pair generations and subsequently monitoring their recombination reactions in a series of porphyrin-quinone based intramolecular ET systems with fixed-distance donor-acceptor centers, as are shown in

Scheme 4. Following these initial reports on the experimental demonstrations of the MI behavior for the ET reactions, subsequently there have been many extensive follow up studies involving different donor-acceptor systems and following various experimental designs, with the aim to realize the MI behavior and also to understand diverse factors that play the role in facilitating or suppressing the MI behavior for the ET reactions under various experimental conditions¹⁰⁵⁻¹²⁶.

Scheme 4. The porphyrin-quinone based intramolecular ET systems used by Wasielewski and coworkers¹⁰⁴ in their study demonstrating the MI behavior experimentally involving intramolecular charge recombination reactions in the photoinduced radical ion-pairs in these chemical systems.

An interesting observation in regard to the MI behavior observed experimentally from many extensive studies is the asymmetric shape of the constructed bell-shaped curves^{1-11,32,102-126}, though from eq. (7) and (8), as given by Marcus ET theory^{45,46}, the inversion behavior should lead to a very symmetric inverted bell-shaped correlation. This aspect is qualitatively demonstrated in Fig. 3 for just a schematic presentation of the facts. To be mentioned that the asymmetry in the experimental MI curves always appeared due to the less stiff and somewhat non-quadratic bending of the curves in the “Marcus Inverted Region” compared to the quite quadratic bending of the curves in the “Normal Marcus Region”, as also qualitatively indicated in Fig. 3.

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Fig. 3. Qualitative presentation of the asymmetric nature of the experimentally observed Marcus inversion curves as compared to the theoretically predicted symmetric bell-shaped curves.

A number of reasons have been put forward to rationalize the asymmetric nature of the experimental MI plots. One of these reasons is the involvement of the high frequency ($h\nu \gg kT$) vibrational modes in modulating the ET reactions, which occur especially at the higher exergonicity region, because in this region the energy released from the ET reactions is sufficient enough to excite the high frequency vibrational modes of the product (P) state formed during the progress of the ET reaction^{1-10,32,45-67}. Other reasons suggested for the observed asymmetry in the experimental MI plots are the donor-acceptor separation dependent electronic coupling element (V_{el}) and solvent reorganization energy (λ_s) for the concerned ET systems, especially at the higher exergonicity region^{1-16,32,26-42,52-67,102-120}. The rationale behind the consideration of influence of the parameters V_{el} and λ_s towards the asymmetry in the MI plots is that both of these parameters are strongly dependent of the separation between the interacting donor-acceptor pairs in the reaction sphere, as given by the eqs. (9) and (10), respectively, and the fact that the average size of the reaction sphere gradually decreases on increasing the reaction exergonicity^{1-16,32,26-42,52-67,102-120}.

$$V_{el,r}^2 = V_{el,0}^2 \exp\{-\beta(r_{AD} - \sigma)\} \quad (9)$$

$$\lambda_s = \frac{e^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_{op}} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_s} \right) \left(\frac{1}{r_A} + \frac{1}{r_D} - \frac{1}{r_{AD}} \right) \quad (10)$$

where r_{AD} is the separation between the D and A centers in the reaction sphere, σ is the contact distance between D and A, r_D and r_A are the radii of the D and A molecules, respectively (considered to be an effective sphere), ϵ_{op} and ϵ_s are the high frequency and static dielectric constants of the solvent, respectively, and e is the charge of an electron. It is realized that at very high exergonicity region the donor-acceptor pairs in the reaction sphere having smaller separations contribute more to the ET reaction than those with higher separations. Accordingly, incorporating the effects of V_{el} and λ_s on the ET kinetics effectively causes an enhancement in the ET rates as otherwise expected without considering these effects of the D-A separations on the observed ET rates^{1-16,102-120}.

Various type of ET reactions for which Marcus Inversion behavior have been observed experimentally without any ambiguity are : (i) intramolecular ET reactions between covalently linked donor and acceptor moieties (often with a suitable spacer in between the donor and acceptor enters)^{1-16,32,35,36,53,113-134} and (ii) charge recombination (CR) reactions taking place in the contact radical ion-pairs subsequent to their formation by a preceding PET reaction¹⁰²⁻¹²⁶. For bimolecular or intermolecular ET reactions, however, observed reaction rates (k_{obs}) in conventional homogeneous media hardly show the expected Marcus inversion behavior. In these cases the most common observation is that the k_{obs} value increases initially with $-\Delta G^0$ at the lower exergonicity region (normal region) but it saturates finally to a limiting value, typically to the bimolecular diffusion controlled rate constant (k_d ; *cf.* Scheme 2), at the higher exergonicity region, without showing any inversion behavior^{1-16,32,35,36,53,113-138}. Typical of such behavior is commonly known as the Rehm-Weller behavior, after the scientists D. Rehm and A. Weller, who observed such a behavior for the first time in the year 1970 for bimolecular ET reactions in a homogeneous solution¹²⁷. Typical feature of the Rehm-Weller behavior in the k_{obs} vs ΔG^0 plot is schematically shown in Fig. 4 along with the otherwise expected Marcus

Fig. 4. Qualitative presentation of the Rehm-Weller behavior for the observed bimolecular ET rates in homogeneous solutions. Expected inversion at very high exergonicity region is also qualitatively indicated.

inversion behavior that remains obscured for bimolecular ET reactions in conventional homogeneous solvents.

Following the reaction steps involved in bimolecular ET reactions, as shown in Scheme 2, the experimentally observed rate constant, k_{obs} , as would be estimated following the decay kinetics of isolated A^* molecules, should be expressed in its simplified form as,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_d}{1 + \frac{k_{-d}}{k_{et}}} = \frac{k_d}{1 + \frac{k_d}{K_{eq}k_{et}}} = \frac{k_d}{1 + \left(\frac{k_d}{K_{eq}}\right) \frac{1}{v \exp(-\Delta G^*/RT)}} \quad (11)$$

where $K_{eq} = (k_d/k_{-d})$, the equilibrium constant for the precursor/encounter complex formation and v is the pre-exponential factor, having the same meaning as discussed with respect to eq. (1), given earlier. Considering eq. (11) and observing that k_{obs} values finally saturates to the k_d value at higher exergonicity region, Rehm and Weller proposed an empirical expression for ΔG^* in terms of the ΔG^0 and λ values, as given by eq. (12), which is distinctly different than the quadratic relation proposed by the Marcus ET theory (*cf.* eq. (7)).

$$\Delta G^* = \left(\frac{\Delta G^0}{2}\right) + \left\{ \left(\frac{\Delta G^0}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\lambda}{4}\right)^2 \right\}^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

As suggested from eq. (12), on increasing the reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$), the ΔG^* value will gradually decrease asymptotically tending toward zero, which can be pictorially represented as in Fig. 5A. Thus, following eqs. (11) and (12), the k_{obs} value will gradually increase in an asymptotic manner with the increasing exergonicity of the reaction, tending toward the saturation limit of the k_d value at the higher exergonicity region, as pictorially represented in Fig. 5B. That the bimolecular ET rates with the reaction exergonicity are usually seen to follow the typical

Fig. 5. Conceptual presentations of (A) changes in the ΔG^* with reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$) and (B) the variations of k_{obs} values with reaction exergonicity as governed by Rehm-Weller relations (eqs. (11) and (12)) for bimolecular ET reactions in polar solvent media.

Rehm-Weller behavior than the theoretically predicted Marcus Inversion behavior, this aspect had been the subject of great concern to the researchers for many decades. This had been especially so because quite convincing Marcus Inversion behaviors could be obtained experimentally not only for a large number of intramolecular ET systems but also for the charge recombination reactions in various contact ion-pairs^{1-16,32,35,36,53,102-134}, though the same inversion behavior remained always obscured for bimolecular ET reactions in conventional solvents. Accordingly, the long lasting quest had been, what could be the factors that actually resist the observation of the Marcus inversion behavior for bimolecular ET reactions in the solution phase and is there any possibility to overcome these influences by some suitable experimental designs so that the Marcus Inversion behavior can also be observed easily for the bimolecular ET reactions as well?

Though observation of Marcus inversion behavior is still a rare finding for bimolecular ET reactions, it is however, quite convincingly understood from extensive theoretical and experimental studies that irrespective of the trends observed for the k_{obs} vs ΔG^0 plots, the observed results can be justifiably rationalized within the framework of the Marcus outer-sphere ET theory. Accordingly, Marcus ET theory has been realized as the most versatile theoretical basis to accommodate all the different findings involving the ET reactions, albeit with the incorporations of suitable refinements, as may be required based on the experimental conditions. Therefore, in the expression of k_{obs} for the bimolecular ET reactions, as given by eq. (11), the term ΔG^* would better be considered as given by eq. (7) in the Marcus ET theory than eq. (12) given empirically by Rehm-Weller. Accordingly, one can expect that for the lower reaction exergonicities, where $-\Delta G^0 \ll \lambda$, the ΔG^* will be quite high to make the intrinsic k_{et} much lower than k_{d} . In this situation, precursor/encounter complexes are formed faster than the intrinsic ET process, making the k_{obs} effectively similar to k_{et} (*cf.* eqs. (8) and (11)). Similarly for the exceedingly higher exergonicity

region, where $-\Delta G^0 \gg \lambda$, the ΔG^* will again become quite high, making k_{obs} once again effectively similar to k_{et} (*cf.* eqs. (8) and (11)). For the intermediate reaction exergonicities, however, ΔG^* being reasonably small, the k_{et} value will be high enough such that $k_{\text{et}} \gg k_{\text{d}}$. In these situations, therefore, k_{obs} will be effectively determined by the formation rate (k_{d}) of the encounter complex than the intrinsic ET rate. The typical of these situations, as would be reflected in the k_{obs} vs ΔG^0 correlation curves, are conceptually shown in Fig. 4 along with the conceptual presentation of the predicted Marcus inversion behavior and the often encountered Rehm-Weller behavior observed for most of the bimolecular ET reactions conducted in conventional homogeneous solvents. To be mentioned, however, that the involvement of the high frequency vibrational modes^{1-11,32,47-53,63-67} and the reaction exergonicity dependent changes in the V_{el} and λ value^{1-11,32,115-120} (*cf.* eqs. (9) and (10)), as we have discussed earlier, can often cause the ET rates at higher exergonicity region to be much higher than expected from the simple quadratic consideration of ΔG^* expression and thus can move the expected inversion region to much higher exergonicities, causing the Rehm-Weller behavior to be the only feature observed for such bimolecular ET reactions.

Bimolecular electron transfer kinetics studied through fluorescence quenching measurements under diffusive and non-diffusive conditions

In most of the bimolecular PET studies in homogeneous solutions, conventional fluorescence quenching measurements are carried out using very low fluorophore (F) concentration (typically μM range), where reasonably lower quencher (Q) concentrations (typically tens of mM range) can be sufficient to give enough fluorescence quenching to extract the required k_{obs} values as the bimolecular quenching constants (k_{q}), defined by the Stern-Volmer quenching kinetics¹²⁷⁻¹³⁹, without involving any transient effect (instantaneous or ultrafast quenching in the preexisting close proximity F-Q pairs, without involving diffusion) in the quenching process. In these experiments,

the quencher concentrations are still being much higher than the excited fluorophore concentration, the PET reaction can satisfactorily be considered as a pseudo-first process¹²⁷⁻¹³⁹. Therefore, the observed decay kinetics for the excited F* in the absence and in presence of Q as one would measure from time-resolved (TR) fluorescence studies can be expressed, respectively, as,

$$F^* = F_0^* \exp\{-(\tau_0^{-1})t\} \quad (13)$$

$$F_Q^* = F_0^* \exp\{-(\tau_0^{-1} + k_q[Q])t\} \\ = F_0^* \exp\{-(\tau_Q^{-1})t\} \quad (14)$$

where τ_0 and $\tau_Q = \{-(\tau_0^{-1} + k_q[Q])^{-1}$ are the fluorescence lifetimes of the excited F* in the absence and in the presence of Q. Therefore, in these cases, the standard Stern-Volmer relation from TR fluorescence quenching results can be expressed as¹²⁷⁻¹³⁹,

$$\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_Q} = 1 + k_q\tau_0[Q] \quad (15)$$

To be mentioned here, in regard to the PET reactions, the F* here can represent the excited acceptor (A*) while the Q will represent the ground state donor (D), as we have discussed earlier. Similarly, one can also consider F* to represent a D* and Q to represent a ground state A, if the PET reaction involves the excited state of the donor and the ground state of the acceptor molecules.

As eq. (15) suggests, the τ_0/τ_Q vs [Q] plot should follow a linear correlation. This linearity is invariably observed when quenching process occurs strictly under diffusive condition (*cf.* Scheme 2) and such a situation can be maintained beyond doubt when the quencher concentrations used are reasonably low, typically in tens of mM range¹²⁷⁻¹³⁹. As Scheme 2 and eq. (11) suggest, under diffusive condition, the k_q (= k_{obs}) value will reach its maximum limit to k_d when ET reaction becomes diffusion controlled (because $k_d \ll$ intrinsic k_{et}), and this is the situation that leads to the Rehm-Weller behavior¹²⁷ discussed earlier. In the conventional low viscosity homogeneous solvents, the typical k_d value is in the range of about $2 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ¹²⁷⁻¹³⁹. Therefore, for a representative fluorophore for which fluorescence lifetime (τ_0) is

typically about 5 ns, a 50 mM quencher concentration can effectively reduce its lifetime (τ_Q) to as low as about 0.83 ns, a reduction large enough for a quenching study exclusively under diffusive condition (*cf.* Scheme 2), completely avoiding any transient effect in the observed quenching kinetics. However, if the quencher concentration in the experimental solution is made substantially higher, say in the molar range, the observed quenching kinetics in these cases will invariably possess a substantial extent of transient effect and the quenching process can no longer be considered solely under diffusive condition because in these situations the non-diffusive effects will also be associated with the observed quenching process. To be noted here that under completely diffusive condition, the quenching of the steady-state (SS) fluorescence intensity of F* will also follow a linear Stern-Volmer relation, which can be expressed in this case as¹²⁷⁻¹³⁹,

$$\frac{I_0}{I_Q} = 1 + k_q\tau_0[Q] \quad (16)$$

where I_0 and I_Q are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and in presence of Q, respectively. Most importantly, under completely diffusive situation the eq. (16) becomes just equal to eq. (15), i.e.¹²⁷⁻¹³⁹,

$$\frac{I_0}{I_Q} = \frac{\tau_0}{\tau_Q} = 1 + k_q\tau_0[Q] \quad (17)$$

Thus, validation of the equality of the time-resolved (τ_0/τ_Q) and steady-state (I_0/I_Q) quenching kinetics as given by eq. (17) is an important criterion to ascertain that a bimolecular quenching process actually occurs under a completely diffusive condition without involving any transient effect.

In conventional low viscosity homogeneous solvents, maintaining the situation represented by eq. (17) for bimolecular ET reaction is quite easy because in these solvents k_d value is quite large ($\sim 2 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1}$) such that fairly substantial extent of fluorescence quenching can be achieved just by using few tens of mM quencher concentration. However, when such a bimolecular ET reaction is carried out in a very high viscosity solvent or in a constrained mi-

cro-heterogeneous medium, where k_d value is inherently very low, use of very high concentrations of the quencher becomes unavoidable to achieve a reasonable extent of fluorescence quenching for a meaningful kinetic analysis to extract the required quenching rate constant. In these cases, obviously, a significant extent of preexisting close proximity F-Q pairs will be present in the system that can undergo instantaneous or ultrafast quenching process following photoexcitation, without involving any diffusion of the reactants and accordingly a substantial extent of transient effect will be present in the observed quenching kinetics for these systems. Understandably thus, for these ET systems the linear Stern-Volmer relationships, as given by eqs. (15), (16) and (17), may not be truly applicable. Accordingly, in these cases, the ET kinetics to be dealt with a quite different approach than using the diffusion reaction kinetics as depicted in Scheme 2 and expressed by eq. (11).

As we understand from the discussion above, the ET reactions in very high viscosity solvents or in constrained micro-heterogeneous media would invariably occur either under non-diffusive condition or under a restricted diffusion condition, such that the transient effect in the observed quenching kinetics becomes inevitable. Interestingly, in these cases, the observed bimolecular ET kinetics are expected to display the Marcus Inversion type of behavior quite easily, because the quenching components arising from transient effects in the preexisting close-proximity F-Q pairs would effectively be equivalent to the intramolecular kind of ET reactions as occur in the chemically bound D-A systems, for which Marcus inversion behavior is a quite common observation, as in these cases the k_{obs} values become the direct measures of the intrinsic k_{et} rates (*cf.* Scheme 1 and related discussion). To be mentioned here that the ET reactions under the so-called restricted diffusion conditions are directly relevant to many ET processes involved in the biological systems, e.g. in photosynthesis, cellular respiration, redox-mediated enzyme catalysis, and so on¹⁻³². Moreover, ET reactions under constrained conditions are also having relevance to various applied areas like information storage, solid

state electronics, molecular electronics, sensing, catalysis, solar energy conversion, photovoltaic, biotechnology, etc.^{1-32,57-67}. Considering all these, the ET reactions under non-diffusive or restricted diffusion conditions are the interesting and important research topics and quite extensive studies have been carried out on such ET reactions to understand the insights of these reactions, aiming their desired controls and efficient utilizations. In the forthcoming sections we will discuss different situations of the bimolecular ET reactions in constrained reaction media, imposing the situations of non-diffusive or restricted diffusion conditions for the observed ET reactions, bringing out the intriguing features of these reactions that are never observed for bimolecular ET reactions in conventional low viscosity homogeneous solvents, investigating the reactions exclusively under the diffusive conditions (*cf.* Scheme 2).

Non-diffusive conditions for bimolecular electron transfer reactions in micro-heterogeneous media

PET reaction in constrained micro-heterogeneous media, like micelles, reverse micelles, vesicles, etc. have attracted considerable research interests for last couple of decades, because of the structural resembles of these assemblies with various biological membranes^{77-90,140-163}. It is generally perceived that such constrained reaction media can help in lingering the lifetime of the radical ion pairs produced in the forward PET reactions quite significantly, by preventing or retarding the back ET or charge recombination reactions, and thereby proving the primary species of the PET reaction to have longer survival times to make them available for the desired follow-up reactions related to their applications in solar energy conversions, photovoltaics, biotechnology, information storage, solid state electronics, molecular electronics, sensing, catalysis, and many others^{1-32,40-44,140-163}. Among different micro-heterogeneous media, the micelles and reverse micelles have attracted the most attentions of the researchers because these systems can be easily formed by using appropriate surfactant solutions and most of the organic donor (D) and acceptor (A) molecules show their preferential solubility inside these self-assembled systems than in the

bulk aqueous phase, making the desired PET reactions to be carried out quite efficiently within these assemblies. The investigations of the PET reactions in micro-heterogeneous media are mainly aimed to understand the effect of the topology of these media on the mechanism and dynamics of the ET reactions and also to explore the possible controls of the ET kinetics through the use of simple tuning methodologies of these self-assembled systems. In the forthcoming discussions, we will bring out several intriguing results that have emerged for the PET studies in such constrained micro-heterogeneous media, especially in regard to the theoretically predicted Marcus inversion behavior for the bimolecular ET reactions^{77-90,140-163}.

For the last about one and half decades, number of research groups, including ours, have carried out extensive studies on bimolecular PET reactions in various self-assembled micro-heterogeneous media to understand the effect of such self-assembled systems on the energetic and kinetics of the ET reactions^{10,69,77-90,140-163}. In these micro-heterogeneous media, the reactant molecules, i.e. D and A, are mainly solubilized within a small region of the self-assembled systems, e.g. within the Stern layer or palisade layer of the micelles, where the surfactant molecules entangle the D and A molecules strongly retarding their diffusion process. Accordingly, the mobility/diffusion of these reactant molecules inside these micro-heterogeneous media becomes highly restricted. In fact, from our elaborate studies, it has been realized that the diffusion of the reactant molecules within these self-assembled micro-heterogeneous media is so drastically retarded that the bimolecular PET reactions in these cases effectively occur under a non-diffusive condition^{10,69,77-80,85-88,140-145}. In other words, the overall PET reactions in such systems mainly occur within those D-A pairs that are already preexisting within the reaction sphere and thus acting as the instantaneous encounter complexes immediately after the photoexcitation process. Therefore, in these cases, the bimolecular PET reactions effectively behave like the intramolecular PET reactions that occur between the bound donor and acceptor moieties in a single

molecule. Thus alike the intramolecular PET reactions, where Marcus Inversion behavior is easily observed, a similar situation is also expected for the bimolecular PET reactions in the self-assembled micro-heterogeneous media to display the Marcus Inversion behavior easily, as really have been observed in number of studies reported by various groups including ours^{10,69,77-90,140-163}.

In conventional low viscosity homogeneous solvents, as the rate of the solvent relaxation is extremely fast, the reactant state (R) involved in a PET reaction always maintains a thermal equilibrium along the solvent relaxation coordinate, which is the effective reaction coordinate (X) in these cases (*cf.* Fig. 1). In these media, therefore, the PET reaction follows a conventional one dimensional ET (1DET) model, as represented in Fig. 1, and in this case the intrinsic ET rate constant is represented by eq. (8), which in more explicit form can be represented by eq. (18) under a non-adiabatic condition ($V_{el} \ll 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and by eq. (19) under an adiabatic condition ($V_{el} \gg 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)^{1-16,45-67,91-101}, as discussed earlier with reference to eqs. (1) and (2).

$$k_{et}(NA) = \frac{2\pi}{h} \frac{V_{el}^2}{\sqrt{4\pi\lambda k_B T}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(\Delta G^0 + \lambda)^2}{4\lambda k_B T}\right\} \quad (18)$$

$$k_{et}(ad) = \frac{1}{\tau_s} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{16\pi k_B T}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(\Delta G^0 + \lambda)^2}{4\lambda k_B T}\right\} \quad (19)$$

In the micro-heterogeneous media, as the overall solvent relaxation rate is unexpectedly slow¹⁶⁴⁻¹⁷⁵, it is expected that unlike in the 1DET model, the R state in these system cannot maintain a thermal equilibrium along the solvent relaxation coordinate during the ET reaction. For example, in the PET reactions, the R state, which will be initially produced with a non-equilibrium solvent reorganization following photoexcitation (*because the dipolar character in the excited state is different than in the ground state*), cannot attend the thermal equilibrium along the solvent coordinate X in a micro-heterogeneous media, because the solvent relaxation in these media occurs very slowly. Accordingly, in these cases, the solvent

Pal : An overview on photoinduced bimolecular electron transfer (ET) in constrained *etc.*

coordinate (X) cannot be considered as the effective reaction coordinate for the ET reactions. Unlike the non-equilibrium situation that persists in these cases along the solvent coordinate X, no such non-equilibrium condition is imposed to the R (or P) state along its intramolecular coordinate q, as the intramolecular reorganization involving low frequency vibrational modes of the reacting systems occur very fast¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁸⁸. Accordingly, the R state would immediately get rid of any unstable situation introduced along q coordinate during its formation through photoexcitation and quickly reestablish the thermal equilibrium along this coordinate and will maintain this equilibrium throughout the progress of the ET reaction¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁸⁸. Therefore, in these cases, instead of the solvent X coordinate, the intramolecular q coordinate would effectively be considered as the reaction coordinate for the ET process. In other words, it is expected that a PET reaction in a constrained micro-heterogeneous medium would effectively occur following a 2DET

Fig. 6. The contours for the reactant and product free energies with the changing X and q coordinates as can be conceptually presented for the 2DET model. The line CC in the contour diagram represents the curve passing through the crossing points of the reactant and product free energy surfaces and thus corresponds to that of the free energy of activations for the ET reactions along q for different X values.

model¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁸⁷, which can be presented schematically by the use of contour diagrams as shown in Fig. 6 and in terms of actual free energy diagrams of the R and P states as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Schematic presentation of 2DET following the free energies of the R and P states. Initial R is at $X = -X_g$ (Free energy curves for excited state at the right part) following photoexcitation of the ground state. Neglecting solvent relaxation this R state continues to oscillate along X axis (*cf.* double sided curved arrow in the excited state) keeping the excess energy of solvent destabilization ($\lambda_s X_g^2$) in the R state unchanged, while the ET reaction proceeds along the intramolecular coordinate q (reaction coordinate; *cf.* upper blue curve in the left part). If the ET reaction involved a fast relaxation solvent, the system would have relaxed completely along X to $X=0$ (*cf.* lower blue curve in the left part) and the reaction would have occurred following the conventional 1DET route.

According to the 2DET model, following photoexcitation, the R state for the PET reaction would invariably be formed with a non-equilibrium X coordinate (i.e. $X \neq 0$) and the system would maintain this non-equilibrium situation all along the ET reaction, because relaxation along the X coordinate is very slow. Thus, following 2DET model, the ET reaction is compelled to proceed along the fast relaxing q coordinate, keeping the excess energy of the R state due to its non-equilibrium salvation along X coordinate ($X \neq 0$) unchanged during the progress of the ET reaction. With this model, thus, it is evident that even if the solvent relaxation is completely frozen, the ET reaction can still occur involving the fast relaxing q coordinate to assist the ET reaction. In this 2DET model, since both q and X coordinates are explicitly used to model the ET reaction, the free energies of the R and P states would also be given explicitly in terms of the two coordinates and considering these coordinates in their normalized forms the X and q dependent G_R and G_P for the reactant and product states can be expressed as¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁸⁷,

$$G_R = \lambda_s X^2 + \lambda_i q^2 \quad (20)$$

$$G_P = \lambda_s (1-X)^2 + \lambda_i (1-q)^2 + \Delta G^0 \quad (21)$$

Further, since the ET reaction effectively occurs independently along the fast relaxing q coordinate for all the possible non-equilibrium distributions of R state along X coordinate (*cf.* Figs. 6 and 7), the effective ET rate ($k_{et,eff}$) will be the sum of all the X-dependent ET rates weighted by the non-equilibrium distribution (ρ) along X, i.e. $k_{et,eff} = \sum k_{et}(X)\rho(X)$. In these situations, considering a non-adiabatic condition ($V_{el} \ll 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) to be applicable for the ET reaction along q, the rate constant $k_{et}(X)$ at any X coordinate would be expressed as¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁸⁷,

$$k_{et}(NA, X) = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} \frac{V_{el}^2}{\sqrt{4\pi\lambda_i k_B T}} \exp \left\{ \frac{-(\Delta G^0 + \lambda_i + \lambda_s - 2\lambda_s |X|)^2}{4\lambda_i k_B T} \right\} \quad (22)$$

It is quite understandable from the above considerations that with the non-equilibrium distributions of R

state along X coordinate, as is the situation for the 2DET reaction, the effective ET kinetics for the system would be strongly non-exponential in nature¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁸⁷. As clearly evident from eq. (22), for any nonzero X value, say $X = X_g \neq 0$, the effective free energy of activation for the ET reaction that occurs along q coordinate (*cf.* Figs. 6 and 7) would be given as,

$$\Delta G^*(X_g) = \frac{(\Delta G^0 + \lambda_i + \lambda_s - 2\lambda_s |X_g|)^2}{4\lambda_i} \quad (23)$$

To be noted that this expression for $\Delta G^*(X_g)$ following 2DET model is distinctly different than the ΔG^* expression (*cf.* eq. (7)) applicable for the ET rate given by eq. (18) following 1DET model, where the total reorganization term λ is explicitly given as $\lambda = \lambda_i + \lambda_s$. To be noted here that in eq. (23) we have deliberately designated the non-equilibrium solvent coordinate as X_g , considering that the R state for the PET reaction would be produced with this non-equilibrium X coordinate immediately after photoexcitation, because the corresponding ground state D-A encounter pair before its excitation was in the solvent equilibrated condition with its free energy minimum at $X = X_g$.

Following the 2DET model, since the R state cannot attain and maintain a thermal equilibrium along X during the ET reaction along q (*cf.* Figs. 6 and 7; eq. (23)), the effective free energy of activation $\Delta G^*(X_g)$ involved in these cases incorporate only a part of λ_s , which can be considered as the effective solvent reorganization energy, λ_s^{eff} , and would be expressed as,

$$\lambda_s^{eff} = \lambda_s - 2\lambda_s |X_g|, \quad (24)$$

It is evident from eq. (24) that the λ_s^{ff} for the 2DET reaction would be much lower than the total λ_s involved in determining the ΔG^* for a typical 1DET reaction (*cf.* eqs. (1), (7), (18) or (19)). For the 2DET reaction¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁸⁸, since the onset of the Marcus Inversion is expected to start at an exergonicity of $-\Delta G^0 = \lambda_i + \lambda_s^{eff}$, while for the 1DET reactions^{1-16,45-67,91-101} the Inversion is expected to start at $-\Delta G^0 = \lambda_i + \lambda_s$, it is evident that for the similar D-A systems the Marcus Inversion for 2DET reaction mechanism (e.g. in con-

strained reaction media) would appear at a relatively lower exergonicity as compared to that happens under the 1DET reaction model (e.g. in fast relaxing homogeneous solvent media)^{10,69,77–80,85–88,140–145}. Therefore, in the 2DET reaction model, since the exergonicity for the onset of Marcus Inversion is shifted favorably towards lower exergonicity (*cf.* eqs. (23) and (24)), it is quite understandable that the constrained micro-heterogeneous media effectively provides a conducive reaction environment for the donor-acceptor systems to realize the Marcus inverted region quite easily than in the fast relaxing conventional homogeneous solvents, because in the latter case one needs to have much higher exergonicity for the reaction to achieve the Marcus inversion behavior^{10,69,77–80,85–88,140–145}.

In the context of the aforementioned aspects, our first study on bimolecular PET reactions in constrained media was carried out in sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) micelles involving a series of coumarin dyes as the electron acceptors and N,N-dimethylaniline (DMAN) as electron donor and thereby we convincingly demonstrated the appearance of Marcus Inversion behavior¹⁴⁰, though for the similar coumarin-DMAN systems in conventional solvent like acetonitrile the observed ET rates followed the typical Rehm-Weller behavior^{131–133}. Following this initial work from our group, quite extensive follow-up studies have been reported in the literature on bimolecular PET reactions in microheterogeneous media and invariably in all the cases the appearance of Marcus Inversion behavior has been documented quite convincingly^{140–156}. Interesting to mention that in all these studies the overall findings are very similar, though in rationalizing the observed facts different research groups have put forward somewhat different explanations. Understandably thus, a consolidated reasoning for the easy appearance of Marcus Inversion behavior for bimolecular PET reactions in constrained micro-heterogeneous media is yet to be arrived at, to justify all the intricacies involved in such ET reactions.

Many of the initial investigations on bimolecular PET reactions in microheterogeneous media were

carried out following simple steady-state (SS) fluorescence intensity quenching and time-resolved (TR) fluorescence quenching kinetics studies^{77–90,140–151}. All these studies have invariably found out that the SS fluorescence intensity quenching always lead to the non-linear Stern-Volmer plots, displaying a positive deviation from the expected linearity from eq. (16). Typical of such plots are shown in Fig. 8. To be mentioned here that for the Stern-Volmer plots in Fig. 8 the quencher concentration has been considered as $[Q]_{\text{eff}}$, which is the calculated quencher concentration in the Stern layer or palisade layers of the micellar system, assuming that the fluorophores and quenchers are mainly solubilized within the Stern/palisade layers of the micelles. Accordingly, the $[Q]_{\text{eff}}$ values were estimated from all the known parameters^{77–80,85–88,140–145} as given by the following equation.

$$[Q]_{\text{eff}} = \frac{N_{\text{agg}} [Q]_{\text{t}}}{V_{\text{L}} \{ [S]_{\text{t}} - \text{cmc} \}} \quad (25)$$

where N_{agg} is the aggregation number of the surfactant (S), $[S]_{\text{t}}$ is the total surfactant concentration used, cmc is its critical micellar concentration for the surfactant solution, $V_{\text{SL/PL}}$ is the volume of the micellar

Fig. 8. Typical SS fluorescence quenching results showing positive deviations in the Stern-Volmer plots for bimolecular ET reactions in a micro-heterogeneous media. Data in this figure correspond to the bimolecular PET studies in Triton-X100 micelles involving N,N-diethyl-*p*-toluidine (DMPT) as the electron donor and (i) C151, (ii) C481 and (iii) C153 as the electron acceptors¹⁴¹.

Stern/palisade layer per mole of the micelle and $[Q]_t$ is the total quencher (amine) concentration as estimated/used for the whole surfactant solution.

From these SS fluorescence intensity quenching results it is quite evident that the typical diffusional quenching scheme, as represented earlier by Scheme 2 for bimolecular ET reactions in conventional homogeneous solvents, is not quite applicable for the reactions in the micro-heterogeneous media. It is clearly indicated from these results that the constrained nature of the micro-heterogeneous reaction media imposes the PET reactions to occur with the involvement of significant extent of the transient quenching effect, which is otherwise not the case for the reactions in conventional low viscosity homogeneous solvent media¹²⁸⁻¹³⁹. In the concerned micro-heterogeneous media, it is expected that the diffusion of the reactants would be largely retarded due to entanglement of the reactants with surfactant chains. Thus, in these cases the PET reactions are logically to be considered to occur effectively under a non-diffusive reaction condition. Therefore, in these cases, the bimolecular PET reactions are expected to occur mainly through the photoexcitation of the preexisting reasonably close-proximity F-Q pairs for which the centre to centre separations between the F and Q moieties are within the dimension of the possible reaction sphere for the ET system, making these PET reactions quite equivalent to the intramolecular (or unimolecular) PET reactions that occur in the chemically bound D-A system (e.g. Schemes 3 and 4). As one can thus visualize, for the PET reactions in constrained micro-heterogeneous media, a distribution of the preexisting D-A pairs, differing in regard to the separations between the interacting D and A moieties, but still within the dimension of the reaction sphere, will participate in the ET reactions following the photoexcitation process, without involving any mutual diffusion of the interacting D and A units in the timescale of the ET reactions. Obviously the preexisting D-A pairs with smaller D-A separations will undergo a relatively faster ET reaction than those with a comparatively larger D-A separations. Therefore, considering the fact that

the population of the D-A pairs having smaller separations will gradually increase on increasing the quencher concentration in the solution, it is quite expected that the fluorescence intensity quenching will gradually become more efficient with the increasing quencher concentration in the micro-heterogeneous media, leading to the quenching process to show a positive deviation in the Stern-Volmer plots, as typically shown in Fig. 8.

In regard to the TR fluorescence quenching kinetics studies also, the bimolecular ET reactions in micro-heterogeneous media display quite different characteristics than in the homogeneous solutions. Thus, it is interestingly observed that in micro-heterogeneous media the fluorescence quenching kinetics always show a non-exponential kinetic behavior^{77-80,85-88,140-145}, which is quite different than the single-exponential quenching kinetics usually observed for the similar PET reactions in low viscosity homogeneous solvents (*cf.* eq. (14)). Typical non-exponential fluorescence quenching kinetics as observed for bimolecular PET reactions in constrained micro-heterogeneous media following either time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) measurements with sub-nanosecond time-resolution or femtosecond fluorescence up-conversion measurements with sub-picosecond resolution are shown in Figs. 9A and B, respectively, for their quick visualization.

Following the aforementioned discussions, it is evident that the observed non-exponential kinetics for bimolecular PET reactions in constrained micro-heterogeneous media arises mainly due to the unusually slow or non-diffusion nature of the concerned reactions such that the positions of the interacting D and A units are hardly changed during the progress of the reaction^{77-80,85-88,140-145}. In these situations, as distribution of the interacting D-A pairs for which the D-A separations are within the reaction sphere will undergo the ET reactions, and since the rates of these reactions are a strong function of the D-A separations (*cf.* eqs. (9), (10) and (22)), the observed PET kinetics in these cases would necessarily show a highly

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non-exponential behavior. Obviously thus, a comprehensive analysis of the kinetic traces under the present situation is a very complicated task. Considering all these, in these cases, the experimentally observed fluorescence kinetic traces are in general fitted following a multi-exponential decay function and the decay parameters thus obtained are used to discuss the correlations between the kinetics and energetic of such ET reactions in constrained micro-heterogeneous media.

Fig. 9. (A) Typical non-exponential fluorescence kinetics observed in TCSPC measurements for PET reactions in micro-heterogeneous media. The fluorescence decay kinetics for the dye (coumarin-522, C522) is single-exponential in the absence of quencher (N,N-diethyl-*p*-toluidine; DMPT) but distinctly non-exponential in the presence of the quencher¹⁴¹. (B) Typical non-exponential fluorescence kinetics as recorded from up-conversion measurements for PET reactions in micro-heterogeneous media. The kinetic trace of the dye (coumarin-153, C153) in the absence of quencher (N,N-dimethylaniline; DMAN) is just flat as expected but the kinetic trace becomes highly non-exponential in the presence of the quencher⁸⁵.

For the TR fluorescence studies as carried out using the TCSPC measurements having typically about sub-nanosecond time resolution, the kinetic traces for most PET reactions in constrained micro-heterogeneous media are in general found to fit quite satisfactorily following a bi-exponential function^{77-90,140-151} and the decay parameters thus estimated are often used to estimate the average lifetime (τ_{av}) values for the fluorophore in the presence of varying quencher concentrations using the following relation^{77-80,85-88,140-145},

$$\tau_{av} = \frac{1}{100} \times \sum B_i \tau_i \quad (26)$$

where B_i is the percentage contribution and τ_i is the lifetime of the *i*-th decay component of the fitted decay. Subsequently, the reduction in the τ_{av} values with the quencher concentration used are correlated following the standard Stern-Volmer relationship, which for the present situations can be expressed as^{77-90,140-151},

$$\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_{av}} = 1 + k_q [Q]_{eff} \quad (27)$$

The purpose of such Stern-Volmer correlation in the present cases is to estimate the average values of the observed reaction rates in the form of the bimolecular quenching constants (i.e. $k_{obs} = k_q$), which are considered as the measure of the effective rate constants for the observed PET reactions in the micro-heterogeneous media.

Important to mention here that the above Stern-Volmer type of analysis of the τ_{av} values estimated from the TR studies using TCSPC measurements with the typical sub-nanosecond time resolution is almost invariably found to follow a linear correlation^{77-80,85-88,140-145}, as defined by eq. (27). Typical such linear τ_0/τ_{av} versus $[Q]_{eff}$ plots are shown in Fig. 10, for which the SS fluorescence quenching data invariably showed a positive deviation from the expected Stern-Volmer linearity as discussed before (*cf.* Fig. 8). As the τ_0/τ_{av} versus $[Q]_{eff}$ plots in the present cases show quite linear Stern-Volmer correlation, it is thus possible to estimate the average reaction rate constants k_q ($= k_{obs}$) from the slopes of these plots quite sat-

isfactorily such that these k_q values can be considered as the effective measures of the observed ET rates for their subsequent correlation with the exergonicity of the concerned ET reactions, to search of the Marcus Inversion behavior^{77–90,140–151}. In these cases, however, when the TR studies are carried out using ultrafast techniques like fluorescence up-conversion measurements having sub-picosecond time resolutions, obviously the simplified relation as given by eq. (27) would no longer remain applicable. In these cases, however, the inverse of the estimated ultrafast decay time constants (τ_{fast}) as obtained from multi-exponential analysis of the kinetic traces can directly be used as the measures of the absolute ET rates^{10,69–72,77,83–86,152,153}, simply as, $k_{\text{et}} = \tau_{\text{fast}}^{-1}$.

As discussed earlier, in low viscosity conventional homogeneous solvents the Marcus Inversion behavior for bimolecular PET reactions mostly remains obscured due to the influence of the reactant diffusions on the observed reaction rates, which effectively leads to the appearance of the typical Rehm-Weller behavior for the k_{obs} versus ΔG^0 plots^{1–16,32,35,36,53,113–138}. Accordingly, in such homoge-

Fig. 10. Typical time-resolved (TR) fluorescence quenching results obtained using TCSPC measurements for bimolecular ET reactions in micro-heterogeneous media. The results show quite good linearity following Stern-Volmer analysis. Data in this figure corresponds to bimolecular ET reactions in Triton-X100 micelles involving (i) C481, (ii) C151 and (iii) C153 dyes as the acceptors and N,N-diethyl-*p*-toluidine (DMPT) as the donor¹⁴¹.

neous solutions, the Marcus inversion behavior for bimolecular PET reactions not only reported for limited cases, but also in most of these reports the observed inversion behavior is not found to be very convincing^{113–120}. In constrained micro-heterogeneous systems like micelles, reverse micelles, vesicles, etc., however, the Marcus Inversion behavior is in general found to be displayed for most of the bimolecular PET systems reported in the literature^{10,69,77–90,140–163}. This is undoubtedly thus a very striking feature for the bimolecular PET reactions in the constrained reaction media, considering that the similar Marcus Inversion behavior is extremely rare to be observed for the similar bimolecular PET systems in the fast relaxing homogeneous solvent media^{1–16,32,35,36,53,113–138}. Fig. 11 shows two typical such results showing clear Marcus Inversion behavior for bimolecular PET reactions, the first one (Fig. 11A) observed in aqueous P123 triblock copolymer micelles using coumarin dyes as the electron acceptors and N,N-dimethylaniline (DMAN) as the electron donor⁷⁹ and the second one (Fig. 11B) in aqueous sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) micelles using hydroxy and amino substituted anthraquinone dyes as the electron acceptors and number of aromatic amines as the electron donors⁸⁰.

An important aspect to be noticed from the k_{obs} versus ΔG^0 correlation plots for the bimolecular PET reactions in constrained micro-heterogeneous media, as is also indicated from the plots in Fig. 11, that the onset of the Marcus Inversion appears at an exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$) which is clearly much lower than the total reorganization energy λ ($= \lambda_s + \lambda_i$) expected for such ET systems. Thus, for the representative Marcus correlation plots shown in Fig. 11, the onset of the Marcus Inversion is seen to appear at an exergonicity of ~ 0.7 eV, whereas in the studied micellar palisade/Stern layer the total reorganization energy λ ($= \lambda_s + \lambda_i$) is supposed to be about 1.2 eV or more^{79,80}, because in these cases the solvent reorganization energy λ_s is estimated to be about 1.0 eV on the basis of the measured dielectric constants in their palisade/Stern layers, and the intramolecular reorganization energy λ_i involving the studied elec-

Fig. 11. The Marcus correlation plots for bimolecular PET reactions in (A) P123 triblock copolymer micelles⁷⁹ and (B) in conventional SDS micelles⁸⁰. Marcus Inversion behavior is clearly indicated in both the cases. Interestingly, the onset of Marcus Inversion in these cases appear at an exergonicity ($-\Delta G^{\circ}$) of ~ 0.7 eV, which is evidently much lower than the expected total reorganization energy λ ($= \lambda_s + \lambda_i$) of about 1.2 eV or more^{79,80}.

tron acceptor-donor systems is expected to be typically in the range of about 0.2–0.3 eV. That the Marcus Inversion appears at a much lower exergonicity than the total reorganization energy (λ) involved in the ET reactions is also found to be a quite common observation for bimolecular ET reactions in the other constrained micro-heterogeneous media reported^{10,69,77–80,85–88,140–145}. Such a shift in the Marcus Inversion towards a lower exergonicity region is in fact realized to be due to the partial contribution of the solvent reorganization energy λ_s towards the free energy of activation (ΔG^*) for the ET reaction, because in these cases the ET reactions occur following a

2DET mechanistic model (due to exceedingly slow solvent relaxation), as we have discussed before (*cf.* Fig. 6 and 7, eq. (22), (23) and (24)).

From the discussions made so far, it is evident that in constrained micro-heterogeneous media due to the non-significant (or slow) diffusion of the reactants within the timescales of the ET reactions (which makes the bimolecular ET reactions quite equivalent to the intramolecular ET reactions) and the exceptionally slow solvent relaxation dynamics in these media (which enforces only a partial contribution of λ_s towards ΔG^* ; *cf.* eqs. (22), (23) and (24)) the Marcus Inversion behavior becomes quite easy to be observed even for the bimolecular PET reactions. The arguments made henceforth in regard to the bimolecular PET reactions in constrained micro-heterogeneous media can logically also be applied for other high viscosity slow relaxing solvents, e.g. the ionic liquid (IL) solvents, for which due to high viscosity of the solvents the diffusion of the reactants and also the solvent relaxation dynamics become inherently very slow. In fact, following the unique Marcus Inversion behavior reported for the bimolecular PET reactions in various micro-heterogeneous media^{10,77–80,85–88,140–145}, a number of follow up studies on bimolecular PET reactions have also been carried out in different ionic liquid solvents and as expected most of these studies also found an easy appearance of the Marcus Inversion behavior^{69,84,89,90,188–191}, though such a behavior is rarely been reported for the bimolecular PET reactions in fast relaxing homogeneous solvents^{1–16,32,35,36,53,113–138}. Therefore, the reported results on bimolecular PET reactions carried out in diverse constrained media have established beyond doubted that under such situations the PET reaction not only occur under a non-diffusive condition but also the reaction follows the unique 2DET mechanistic model such that the Marcus Inversion behavior is easily observed for the studied bimolecular PET reactions in these media, as the inversion region is significantly shifted towards lower exergonicity region as compared to that expected in the fast relaxing homogeneous solvents where the ET reaction in effect occurs following the conventional 1DET mechanistic model.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it has been convincingly established from extensive studies that the PET reactions in micro-heterogeneous media as well in other constrained environments like in IL solvents effectively occurs following a 2DET model than the conventional 1DET model application to fast relaxing conventional homogeneous media. For PET reactions in constrained media as discussed in this article, the ET reaction effectively proceeds along the intramolecular coordinate q , which is reaction coordinate following 2DET model, keeping a non-equilibrium distribution of the reactant state along the solvent coordinate X during the progress of the reaction. This happens because the solvent relaxation being slow in these media, its reorganization cannot compete with the ET reaction. Due to non-equilibrium solvent reorganization during the course of the ET reaction, which is the basis of the 2DET model, in these cases the free energy of activation ΔG^* for the ET reaction can only involve a partial contribution from λ_s and consequently the onset of Marcus Inversion in these cases get largely shifted towards the lower exergonicity region as compared to the 1DET cases that occur in fast relaxing conventional solvents. This shift of the onset of Marcus Inversion towards the lower exergonicity effectively helps in observing the Marcus Inversion behavior easily for the bimolecular PET reactions, as have been reported for bimolecular PET reaction in various constrained reaction media. The high viscosity of constrained reaction media also resists the free diffusion of the reactants, making the PET reactions to occur effectively only in those donor-acceptor pairs that are preexisting within the dimension of the reaction sphere at the moment of their photoexcitation process and thus making these bimolecular ET reactions effectively very similar to the intramolecular PET reactions. Such a situation also in effect helps the Marcus Inversion behavior to be observed easily for bimolecular PET reactions in the studied constrained reaction media. In brief, it is established beyond doubt that the combination of the slow diffusion of the reactants and slow solvent relaxation effectively assist

Marcus Inversion behavior to be observed easily for bimolecular PET reactions in the constrained reaction environments like micro-heterogeneous media and in high viscosity IL solvents. These intriguing results for bimolecular PET reactions in constrained reaction media are undoubtedly very distinct observations because such behaviors for bimolecular PET reactions are hardly observed when reactions are carried out in fast relaxing conventional homogeneous solvents.

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